

**CHARACTERIZATION AND AUTHENTICATION OF SPANISH PDO WINE
VINEGARS USING MULTIDIMENSIONAL FLUORESCENCE AND CHEMOMETRICS**

Rocío Ríos-Reina^a, Saioa Elcoroaristizabal^b, Juan A Ocaña-González^c, Diego L.
García-González^d, José M. Amigo^e, Raquel M. Callejón^{a,*}

^aÁrea de Nutrición y Bromatología, Facultad de Farmacia, Universidad de Sevilla, C/P.
García González nº2, E- 41012, Sevilla, Spain

^b Chemical and Environmental Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering,
University of the Basque Country, Alameda de Urquijo s/n, E-48013 Bilbao, Spain

^c Departamento Química Analítica, Facultad de Química, Universidad de Sevilla, C/P.
García González s/n, E-41012 Sevilla, Spain

^d Instituto de la Grasa (CSIC), Campus University Pablo de Olavide - Building 46, Ctra.
de Utrera, km. 1 E– 41013, Sevilla, Spain

^e Chemometric Analytical Technologies, Department of Food Sciences, Faculty of
Science, University of Copenhagen, Rolighedsvej 30, Frederiksberg CDK-1958,
Denmark

Running Title: Characterization and authentication of Spanish PDO vinegars by
fluorescence and chemometrics.

*Author to whom correspondence should be sent.

E-mail: rcallejon@us.es

1 **Abstract**

2 This work assesses the potential of multidimensional fluorescence spectroscopy
3 combined with chemometrics for characterization and authentication of Spanish
4 Protected Designation of Origin wine vinegars. Seventy-nine vinegars of different
5 categories (aged and sweet) belonging to the Spanish PDOs “*Vinagre de Jerez*”,
6 “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” and “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*”, were analyzed by
7 excitation-emission fluorescence spectroscopy. A visual assessment of fluorescence
8 landscapes pointed out different trends with vinegar categories. PARAllel FACtor
9 analysis (PARAFAC) extracted the potential fluorophores and their values in the PDO
10 vinegars. This information, coupled with different classification methods (Partial Least
11 Square Discrimination Analysis “PLS-DA” and Support Vectors Machines “SVM”), was
12 able to discriminate the wine vinegar category within each PDO, for which SVM models
13 obtained better results (>92% of classification). In each category, SVM also allows the
14 differentiation between PDOs. The proposed methodology could be used as an
15 analysis method for the authentication of Spanish PDO wine vinegars.

16 1. Introduction

17 Vinegar is a product used worldwide as a condiment and food preserving agent,
18 obtained by a double fermentation process (alcoholic and acetic fermentation) of
19 sugary and starchy substrates (FAO, 1998). Vinegar can be produced by different
20 methods and raw materials (such as malt, apple, rice, etc.), among which, wine vinegar
21 is the most commonly produced and consumed vinegar in Mediterranean countries and
22 Central Europe (Polo & Sanchez-Luengo, 1991).

23 For many years, wine vinegar has been considered as a low-cost secondary
24 product spontaneously derived from wine production. However, in recent years wine
25 vinegar has become a valued food product much appreciated in gastronomy. As a
26 result, the demand for high-quality wine vinegars has significantly increased over the
27 last years. In this framework, Spain is one of the major producers of high-quality wine
28 vinegars, including three of the five types of vinegar registered in Europe (Council
29 Regulation (EC) No 510/2006) with a “Protected Designation of Origin” (PDO): “*Vinagre*
30 *de Jerez*”, “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” and “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” (Table I
31 Supplemental Material). The production of these high-quality PDO wine vinegars in
32 Spain is centered in Andalusia, each of them made from the corresponding protected
33 wines (*Jerez, Montilla-Moriles and Condado de Huelva*), which provides singular and
34 specific characteristics to each vinegar. In addition, the production of high-quality
35 vinegars requires an ageing period in wooden butts. During the period of aging, some
36 chemical modifications take place providing them with unique organoleptic properties
37 and higher sensory quality (Morales, Tesfaye, García-Parrilla, Casas, & Troncoso,
38 2002). According to the sweetness, time and method of ageing (“*criaderas and solera*”
39 and “*añada*” system), different categories are considered within each Spanish PDO
40 (Table 1).

41 The longer aging time is directly related to both the higher quality and production
42 costs of these wine vinegars. This fact increases the final market price and makes the
43 quality assurance and authentication of the Spanish PDOs wine vinegars an important
44 issue. For this reason, objective analytical methodologies are required to guarantee the
45 wine vinegar authenticity and fight against frauds. However, the most common
46 analytical techniques used for the characterization and authentication of these vinegars
47 rely on chromatographic methods that are often expensive and time-consuming
48 (Aceña, Vera, Guasch, Busto, & Mestres, 2011; Cirlini, Caligiani, Palla, & Palla, 2011).
49 Thus, in recent years there has been a growing interest in developing rapid,

50 inexpensive, non-destructive and direct methodologies based on non-targeted
51 techniques for food authentication. Fluorescence spectroscopy has been increasingly
52 applied as a competitive, high sensitivity, fast and non-destructive technique in food
53 analysis (Karoui & Blecker, 2011). This spectroscopic technique has been more
54 commonly used in wine (Airado-Rodríguez, Galeano-Díaz, Durán-Merás, & Wold,
55 2009; Azcarate et al., 2015), but rarely adopted for wine vinegar samples (Callejón et
56 al., 2012) and hence, there is still scarce information about vinegar fluorescent
57 components.

58 In this sense, wine vinegar is a very complex multi-component mixture of chemical
59 compounds due to its traditional making procedure, the raw material used and the
60 ageing period and method employed. Some of these chemical compounds are
61 polyphenols, amino acids and vitamins (Airado-Rodríguez, Durán-Merás, Galeano-
62 Díaz, & Wold, 2011), whose presence is related to the wine chemical basis. To handle
63 this complexity, fluorescence multidimensional measurements, such as excitation-
64 emission fluorescence spectroscopy, combined with adequate multi-way methods
65 (Andersen & Bro, 2003; Sádecká & Tóthová, 2007) have been proven to be useful for
66 characterization of complex food matrices (Callejón et al., 2012; Christensen, Becker,
67 & Frederiksen, 2005; Elcoroaristizabal et al., 2016; Lenhardt, Bro, Zeković, Dramićanin,
68 & Dramićanin, 2015). Measuring the emission spectra at different excitation
69 wavelengths results into a bi-dimensional Excitation-Emission Matrix (EEM), which
70 contains unique information of each measured sample. Therefore, a three dimensional
71 array is obtained when all the samples are gathered together, so requiring an
72 appropriate data processing for its interpretation.

73 An adequate multiway method, such as PARAllel FACtor Analysis (PARAFAC), can
74 be used to decompose fluorescence EEMs into different independent groups of
75 fluorescence components (fluorophores), as well as their relative concentration
76 (scores) in each sample (Bro, 1997). The information provided by the resolved
77 fluorophores has been successfully applied in food quality control, since it can reveal
78 clearer insights into the relationships between the intrinsic food properties and the
79 quality of the product. For instance, EEM-PARAFAC has been applied for monitoring
80 the changes occurring during the storage and production of different food samples
81 (Christensen, Becker, & Frederiksen, 2005; Elcoroaristizabal et al., 2016) and their
82 characterization (Lenhardt et al., 2015; Tena, Aparicio, & García-González, 2012).
83 Furthermore, the information obtained after EEM data decomposition by PARAFAC

84 modeling could be coupled with different classification methods in order to characterize
85 and classify different food products or detect fraudulent samples (Callejón et al., 2012).

86 There are numerous classification algorithms such as Partial Least Square
87 Discrimination Analysis (PLS-DA), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector
88 Machines (SVM) and Soft Independent Modelling of Class Analogy (SIMCA) (Cover &
89 Hart, 1967; Vapnik, 1999; Wold, 1966; Wold, 1976). Among them, Partial Least
90 Squares-Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) and Support Vectors Machines (SVM) are
91 two of the most common used ones. PLS-DA is a supervised class-modelling method
92 used for building linear discriminant models (Nocairi, Qannari, Vigneau, & Bertrand,
93 2005), which has been successfully applied to a wide variety of food matrices for
94 classification purposes (Azcarate, Cantarelli, Pellerano, Marchevsky, & Camiña, 2013;
95 Lenhardt et al., 2015; Liu, He, & Wang, 2008). The main advantage of the PLS-DA
96 approach is the ability of handling highly collinear and noisy data. However, one of the
97 main issues is that PLS-DA models need a sufficient and balanced amount of samples
98 for each class; and sometimes it is difficult to acquire sufficient samples of some
99 classes, due to their cost of production or their non-availability in the market. Moreover,
100 classes that are not effectively separated linearly are common in food products.
101 Support Vector Machines (SVM) is an effective non-linear machine learning technique
102 suitable for both classification and regression analysis (Xu, Zomer, & Brereton, 2006).
103 In comparison to PLS-DA, the main advantage of SVM is its flexibility in modelling
104 complex classification problems that are non-linear. A common disadvantage of SVM is
105 the lack of transparency of the results, since there are no statistics such as scores and
106 loadings available for easy visualization.

107 Several researchers have tested the SVM's performance in different food
108 authentication problems obtaining better results than other traditional classification
109 methods. For instance, Acevedo et al. (2007) (Acevedo, Jiménez, Maldonado,
110 Domínguez, & Narváez, 2007) observed that SVM performed better than SIMCA, k-
111 NN, and PLS-DA for discrimination of wines according to their PDO, which also
112 enabled the selection of the most relevant UV-Vis wavelengths for samples
113 classification. In the same way Callejón et al. (2012) (Callejón et al., 2012) proved that
114 SVM in conjunction with excitation-emission fluorescence spectroscopy was a more
115 adequate methodology than PLS-DA for the classification of sherry vinegars according
116 to their ageing time. However, the aforementioned study was only focused on the
117 classification of a limited number of wine vinegar categories (aged vinegars) belonging
118 to one Spanish PDO ("*Vinagre de Jerez*").

119

120 In this context, the aim of this work was to investigate the feasibility of using
121 excitation-emission fluorescence spectroscopy combined with several chemometric
122 techniques for characterization and classification of the three Spanish PDOs wine
123 vinegars and their commercialized categories. First, EEM data will be analyzed by
124 PARAFAC in order to characterize spectroscopically and chemically different
125 commercialized wine vinegar categories (aged and sweet) according to each Spanish
126 PDO. Then, these results will be used to build reliable classification models able to
127 differentiate between the wine vinegar categories corresponding to each Spanish PDO,
128 and each PDO within the same wine vinegar category.

129

130 **2. Materials and Methods**

131

132 **2.1 Wine vinegar samples**

133 Seventy-nine wine vinegar samples from the three Spanish PDOs coming from
134 several producers were analyzed in this study (Table 1): 30 “*Vinagre de Jerez*”, 18
135 “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” and 21 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” samples.
136 Among the aged categories, these vinegars are aged by the traditional system called
137 “*criaderas and solera*”, except for the “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva Añada*” which is
138 aged by using the static aging system called “*añada*”. Regarding the “*Pedro Ximenez*”
139 category, it should be highlighted that this sweet category differs from the aged
140 category not only by the aging time but also by other factors such as their different
141 production process. Thus, they are produced by the addition of must of raisined “*Pedro*
142 *Ximenez*” grapes (in the case of “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*”) or the addition of “*Pedro*
143 *Ximenez*” wine to the vinegar. All the samples were purchased from local wineries
144 working in compliance with current regulations of each Spanish PDO. The samples
145 were collected in triplicate and stored in amber vials at room temperature until the
146 analysis.

147 Within each PDO, a different number of samples were collected for the established
148 categories (aged and sweet) according to the production/sale rates of each category
149 during the last years (2014-2015). In these years, the general trend for the three
150 Spanish PDOs reveals a higher production of the categories with less ageing time due
151 to market trends. For instance, “*Vinagre de Jerez*” (JCR) represented approximately
152 60% of total sales in the PDO “*Vinagre de Jerez*”, while sales of “*Vinagre de Jerez*
153 *Reserva*” (JRE) and “*Vinagre de Jerez Gran Reserva*” (JGR) accounted for 40% and
154 1% of the total, respectively. Similarly, “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” (CSC)
155 category had the highest sales growth up 38% of the total. Meanwhile among the aged

156 categories of “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDO, the most commercialized vinegar
157 categories were, in decreasing order: “*Solera*” (CSO), “*Reserva*” (CRE) and “*Añada*”
158 (CAN). In the same way, “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles Crianza*” (MCR) was the most
159 commercialized one of the “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDO due to the recent
160 incorporation to the Spanish PDOs.

161 **2.2 Fluorescence analysis**

162 Fluorescence measurements were recorded using a Varian Cary-Eclipse
163 fluorescence spectrophotometer (Varian Iberica, Madrid, Spain), equipped with two
164 Czerny-Turner monochromators, and a Xenon discharge lamp pulsed at 80 Hz with a
165 half peak height of $\sim 2 \mu\text{s}$ (peak power equivalent to 75 kW). A high-performance R298
166 photomultiplier tube detector was used for collection of the fluorescence spectra. Wine
167 vinegar samples were directly analysed without sample pre-treatment by pipetting them
168 into 3.5 mL quartz cuvettes before measurement. Standard quartz cells (Hellma
169 Analytics, Müllheim, Germany) of 1 cm path length were used to carry out the
170 measurements in a Peltier thermostatted cuvette holder ($25.00 \pm 0.05 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The
171 spectrometer was interfaced to a computer with Cary-Eclipse software for spectral
172 acquisition and exportation.

173 The fluorescence Excitation-Emission Matrices (EEMs) were obtained by varying
174 the excitation wavelength (λ_{ex}) ranging between 250 and 700 nm (every 5 nm), and
175 recording the emission spectra (λ_{em}) from 300 to 800 (every 2 nm). For these
176 measurements, excitation and emission slits were both set at 5 nm, and the scan rate
177 was fixed to 1200 nm min^{-1} . The system was wavelength calibrated every day by
178 means of the water Raman peak to account for a possible wavelength drift of the
179 instrument. EEMs were registered by triplicate for each sample and preprocessed in
180 order to avoid noisy and non-informative areas by selecting shorter spectral ranges (λ_{ex}
181 from 250 to 680 nm, and λ_{em} from 310 to 800 nm).

182

183 **2.3 Software and data analysis**

184 EEM data analysis was performed by using the PLS_Toolbox 7.9.5 (Eigenvector
185 Research Inc., Wenatchee, WA) working under Matlab v.8.5.0 environment (The
186 Mathworks Inc., Natick, MA). Before the analysis, EEMs data were corrected for –
187 Rayleigh and Raman scattering (Elcoroaristizabal, Bro, García, & Alonso, 2015) – by
188 removing and replacing the scattering areas with interpolated values by using the
189 FLUCUT function included in the PLS_Toolbox. FLUCUT Removes Rayleigh scattering
190 (and possibly Raman) by inserting NaN and 0 values in Excitation-Emission Matrices

191 (EEMs) where the Rayleigh bands are. Alternatively, FLUCUT may also be used to
192 generate weights that can be used for deweighting (instead of eliminating) these
193 regions.

194 2.3.1 Parallel Factor Analysis (PARAFAC)

195 PARAllel FACtor models were performed on the corrected EEM data in order to
196 extract the relevant information and develop models for: (1) different wine vinegar
197 categories belonging to the same Spanish PDO, and (2) similar wine vinegar
198 categories belonging to different Spanish PDOs.

199 Before modelling, the EEM landscapes corresponding to the same Spanish
200 PDO (1) were rearranged into a three-dimensional structure (\mathbf{X}) of size (3 replicated
201 samples $\times \lambda_{em} \times \lambda_{ex}$): 90 \times 246 \times 87 for the PDO “*Vinagre de Jerez*”, 54 \times 246 \times 87 for
202 the PDO “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*”, and 63 \times 246 \times 87 for the PDO “*Vinagre de*
203 *Condado de Huelva*”. In a similar way, the EEM landscapes corresponding to similar
204 wine vinegar categories but different Spanish PDOs (2) were organized into a three-
205 way array (\mathbf{X}) of size (3 replicated samples $\times \lambda_{em} \times \lambda_{ex}$): 78 \times 246 \times 87 for “*Crianza*”, 66
206 \times 246 \times 87 for “*Reserva*” category, and 27 \times 246 \times 87 for “*Pedro Ximenez*” categories.
207 No PARAFAC analysis was carried out for the “*Gran Reserva*” category due to the
208 limited number of samples.

209 Then, each three-way dataset (\mathbf{X}) was decomposed by PARAFAC (Bro, 1998).
210 The proper number of factors for each model was determined by using the CORE
211 CONSistency DIAgnostic test (CORCONDIA) (Bro & Kiers, 2003), the percentage of
212 variance explained by the model and the visual inspection of the recovered spectral
213 profiles and residuals. Non-negative constraints for all modes (concentrations and both
214 spectral profiles) were applied to obtain meaningful chemical solutions.

215

216 2.3.2 Classification methods

217 Partial Least Squares-Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) (Nocairi et al., 2005) and
218 Support Vectors Machines (SVM) (Vapnik, 1999) algorithms were used to build
219 classification models for discrimination the wine vinegar category within each Spanish
220 PDO. On the one hand, PLS-DA is a classification method based on partial least
221 squares regression (PLS) that transforms the data into a set of linear latent variables
222 for predicting the dependent or class variable, making models that allow the maximum
223 separation among classes. The class variable forms a so-called dummy matrix that
224 indicates whether a sample belongs to a certain class or category. In our study, three

225 different wine vinegar categories were considered in each Spanish PDO, therefore, the
226 dimensions of each dummy matrix was 3x3.

227 On the other hand, SVM is a relative new chemometric tool based on the statistical
228 learning theory (SLT). It is a supervised learning method that searches for the optimal
229 separating hyperplane between the different data classes by maximizing the distance
230 between the hyperplane and the closest samples of the training set (the support
231 vectors), keeping the classification error as low as possible (Xu et al., 2006). Only two
232 parameters need to be tuned in SVM, including C (cost) and the kernel parameter γ in
233 Gaussian kernel function. C is a tuning parameter, which weights in-sample
234 classification errors and controls the generalization ability of an SVM. Moreover, within
235 the different kernel functions, an appropriate γ parameter is related to a stable
236 generalization performance. Furthermore, this method does not need a large number of
237 samples to be trained, it is not affected by the presence of outliers and it has been
238 successfully applied to solve a variety of practical classification problems (Acevedo et
239 al., 2007; Liu et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2006).

240 As the results obtained in our study for the classification of wine vinegar categories
241 within each PDO showed that SVM developed better classification models, only
242 Support Vectors Machines (SVM) was used to build classification models for
243 distinguishing the Spanish PDOs in each similar wine vinegar category ("*Crianza*",
244 "*Reserva*" and "*Pedro Ximenez*"). For both approaches, scores of each sample from
245 PARAFAC models were used, 95% confidence intervals were considered for the
246 classification models and vinegar samples were randomly divided into two groups.

247 The first group of samples (training set), comprising the 75% of samples, was used
248 for calibration and internal validation of the models by means of a venetian blinds
249 cross-validation procedure. For discrimination of the wine vinegar category within each
250 Spanish PDO, this dataset (samples analysed in triplicate) was formed by 63 ("*Vinagre*
251 *de Jerez*"), 33 ("*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*"), and 39 ("*Vinagre de Condado de*
252 *Huelva*") samples. Meanwhile, this dataset consisted of 54 ("*Crianza*"), 48 ("*Reserva*"),
253 and 18 ("*Pedro Ximenez*") samples, in order to distinguish the Spanish PDO
254 corresponding to each wine vinegar category.

255 The second group with the remaining samples (test set) was used as external
256 independent dataset to evaluate the discriminative power of the models (external
257 validation). This dataset was formed by 25% of the samples, and consisted of (samples
258 analyzed in triplicate): 21 ("*Vinagre de Jerez*"), 15 ("*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*"), and
259 18 ("*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*") samples, in order to discriminate the wine

vinegar category within each Spanish PDO. For differentiating the Spanish PDO in each wine vinegar category, this dataset was formed by (samples analyzed in triplicate): 24 (“Crianza”), 18 (“Reserva”), and 9 (“Pedro Ximenez”) samples. Afterwards, the samples belonging to each dataset were randomly selected making sure that in both datasets at least one sample, with the corresponding replicates, of each category/PDO was included. Samples belonging to “Gran Reserva” and “Añada” category in each PDO (JGR, MGR and CAN) with a low number of samples (≤ 2) were not used. Further information about the number of samples used in each case for calibration and external validation can be found in Table II (Supplementary Material).

The statistical assessment of the quality of both classification models was carried out by means of the comparison of the sensitivity, specificity and classification error of calibration (CAL), cross-validation (CV) and prediction (PRED) parameters (Margraf, Santos, de Andrade, van Ruth, & Granato, 2016) according to Eqs. (5) and (6):

$$\text{Sensitivity (\%)} = [\text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FN})] * 100\% \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Specificity (\%)} = [\text{TN} / (\text{TN} + \text{FP})] * 100\% \quad (6)$$

whereby TP and TN represent the number of samples correctly classified as their real class (e.g. the number of JCR samples predicted as JCR and the number of MCR samples predicted as MCR samples, respectively). On the other hand, FP and FN represent the number of samples misclassified (e.g. the JCR samples assigned to MCR class and MCR samples assigned to JCR class, respectively).

280

281 **3. Results and discussion**

282

283 **3.1 Fluorescence landscapes of the Spanish PDO wine vinegars**

Typical fluorescence landscapes of several samples belonging to the different wine vinegar categories of each Spanish PDO are shown in **Figure 1** (after removing and replacing the first and second order Rayleigh scattering). As it can be observed, the shape of the EEM spectra varies within the same Spanish PDO, which allows us to confirm *a priori* differentiation according to the wine vinegar category (aged or sweet).

A visual assessment of the fluorescence features of the aged categories points out a general tendency for the spectral maxima to be shifted towards longer excitation and emission wavelengths with the aging of the vinegars. Furthermore, similar fluorescence maxima were observed for the different Spanish PDOs wine vinegars according to the aging period. In general, vinegars with a minimum of 6 months of aging (JCR, MCR

294 and CSO) show their maximum peaks at 370/450 nm for both excitation/emission
295 wavelengths ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$), whereas the maximum peaks corresponding to the “Reserva”
296 category (JRE, MRE and CRE) appear at higher wavelengths, around 370-470 nm of
297 λ_{ex} and 470-550 nm of λ_{em} . Finally, the most aged “Gran Reserva” category samples
298 (JGR, MGR and CAN) show their maxima at 470-500 nm of excitation and 550-600 nm
299 of emission wavelengths, following the general observed trends. The spectral features
300 of the wine vinegars without aging period (CSC), which shows maximum peaks at the
301 shortest wavelengths (around 370/440 nm $\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$), also confirm this tendency.
302 Interestingly, some samples of the “Reserva” category (e.g. “*Vinagre de Montilla-*
303 *Moriles*” PDO, “Reserva” sample “MRE” in Figure 1) show two different maximum
304 peaks probably due to the broader aging period, which can vary from 24 to 120 months
305 (“*Vinagre de Jerez*” PDO and “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDO) or even to longer
306 periods (“*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDO) (Table 1). These observed spectral
307 features are probably related to the different chemical complexity of the aged
308 categories. In fact, a similar fluorescence trend with the aging of wine samples was
309 observed by Airado-Rodríguez et.al (2011), whose fluorescence landscapes showed a
310 tendency to increase the emission at longer wavelengths with the ageing of the wine
311 samples, due an increase in concentration of fluorescence substances (Airado-
312 Rodríguez et al., 2011).

313 In contrast, the fluorescence landscapes of the sweet vinegar categories, denoted
314 as “*Pedro Ximenez*” (JPX and MPX) show a highly intense fluorescent area between
315 550-570 nm and 600-650 nm of excitation and emission wavelengths, respectively.
316 Indeed, these sweet vinegars show their excitation and emission maxima even at
317 longer wavelengths than the ones corresponding to the aged categories. This
318 phenomenon could be explained by the different production and composition of the
319 sweet vinegars in comparison with the aged categories. Thus, the sweet vinegars are
320 produced with the addition of “*Pedro Ximenez*” Sherry wine in the case of “*Vinagre de*
321 *Jerez*” PDO (containing at least 60 g/L of reducing material from this wine) (Council
322 Regulation (EC) No 510/2006), or adding must of raisined “*Pedro Ximenez*” grapes
323 during the maturing process for the “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDO (Council
324 Regulation (EC) No 510/2006). These sweet vinegars have a high carbohydrate
325 content (glucose and fructose) and other compounds (brown pigments and volatile
326 compounds) produced by a Maillard reaction of the carbohydrates and free amino
327 acids (Casale, Sáiz Abajo, González Sáiz, Pizarro, & Forina, 2006), which may be
328 responsible for the observed fluorescence at longer excitation and emission
329 wavelengths.

330 From these observations, it is clear that the fluorescence landscapes of these
331 Spanish PDOs vinegars contain several fluorophores that are highly overlapped in both
332 excitation and emission spectra. In this sense, further decomposition of EEM spectra
333 by PARAFAC will help to clarify the potential fluorophores present in each vinegar
334 category.

335 **3.2 Potential fluorophores of the Spanish PDO wine vinegars**

336 Three individual PARAFAC models were built in order to extract the excitation and
337 emission profiles of the main fluorophores present in the Spanish PDOs vinegars (as
338 described in section 2.3.1). The optimum number of factors for each PARAFAC model
339 was selected comparing the quality parameters of the models built for an increasing
340 number of factors (ranging from one to seven). Specifically, the best PARAFAC models
341 obtained for each Spanish PDO were 5-factor PARAFAC models for the “*Vinagre de*
342 *Jerez*” and “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDOs, and a 4-factor PARAFAC model for the
343 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDO. The obtained models were enough robust,
344 explaining more than 99% of the variance with a core consistency over zero (Table III
345 Supplementary Material), and represented the underlying chemical spectra of the
346 fluorophores present in these vinegars. Figure 2 includes the PARAFAC loadings
347 (excitation and emission spectra) of the extracted factors present in each Spanish PDO
348 vinegar, whose corresponding fluorescence emission and excitation maxima are listed
349 in Table IV (Supplementary Material). The fluorescent loading patterns of the modelled
350 factors can be matched to fluorophores described in the literature (Airado-Rodríguez et
351 al., 2011; Dufour, Letort, Laguet, Lebecque, & Serra, 2006; Elcoroaristizabal et al.,
352 2016). However, it is important to note that vinegar contains a wide variety of naturally
353 occurring fluorescent compounds, being each emission/excitation profiles a sum of
354 related fluorescent molecules and not only to a single one (Airado-Rodríguez et al.,
355 2011). The difference in these modelled factors is probably related to the different
356 chemical composition of these vinegars as a consequence of the different raw
357 materials (wines) and production and ageing processes for each Spanish PDO. This is
358 corroborated by the variation in the score values of the fluorophores modelled for each
359 Spanish PDO according to the vinegar category (Table V Supplementary Material).

360 The first factor (F1, blue line in Figure 2) of the PDO “*Vinagre de Jerez*” has a
361 maximum excitation centered at 465 nm and a maximum emission around 535 nm.
362 According to Airado-Rodríguez et al. (2011), this factor could be related to vitamin B2
363 and its principal forms such as riboflavin, Flavin mononucleotide (FMN), and Flavin
364 adenine dinucleotide (FAD). In contrast, F1 appears at lower wavelengths, specifically

365 at 375/460 nm and 370/470 nm ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$), for the “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” and
366 “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDOs, respectively. In these PDOs, and taking into
367 account these wavelengths, F1 could be due to the presence of coumarins, tannins
368 and other unknown fluorescent compounds originating from wooden casks (Tóthová &
369 Sádecká, 2008), as well as phenols and flavonols, usually in abundance in these
370 vinegars and naturally presented in wines (Airado-Rodríguez et al., 2011; Sádecká &
371 Tóthová, 2007).

372 The second factor (F2, red line in Figure 2) has a similar profile for the three PDOs
373 with an excitation and emission maxima between 400-420 nm and 480-505 nm
374 respectively. 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), which has been determined in vinegars
375 as a product being formed during the Maillard reaction (García Parrilla, Heredia, &
376 Troncoso, 1999), could match with the wavelengths of F2 according to Zhu et al., 2009
377 (Zhu, Ji, Eum, & Zude, 2009). Furthermore, caramel, which is frequently added to
378 vinegars as a colorant, showed a maximum excitation/emission wavelength at 390-
379 410/482-498 nm according to Sádecká et al., 2009 (Sádecká, Tóthová, & Májek, 2009),
380 and Tóthová et al., 2008 (Tóthová & Sádecká, 2008). Its presence in these vinegars
381 could be also related to this second factor.

382 The third factor (F3, yellow line in Figure 2) of “*Vinagre de Jerez*” PDO is a peak
383 centered at 500 nm (λ_{ex}) and 580 nm (λ_{em}). This component could be associated to
384 brown pigments produced by some acetic bacteria strains present in vinegar (Polo &
385 Sanchez-Luengo, 1991) since they showed similar excitation/emission wavelengths.
386 However, in “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDO, this factor F3 shows excitation and
387 emission maxima around 470/550 nm, which agrees with the presence of vitamin B2
388 and its principal forms (Lenhardt et al., 2015). Finally, the third factor of “*Condado de*
389 *Huelva*” PDO is centered at 300/425 nm ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$), and these wavelengths could be
390 associated with the phenolic compounds present in these vinegars (Rodríguez-
391 Delgado, Malovaná, Pérez, Borges, & García Montelongo, 2001).

392 The fourth factor (F4, purple line in Figure 2) has 340/420 nm and 350/440 nm of
393 excitation and emission maxima for the “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” and “*Vinagre de*
394 *Jerez*” PDOs. According to the literature, the excitation/emission wavelengths of this
395 factor could be related to phenolic compounds, the best known fluorescent molecules
396 naturally present in wine that differ in accordance to the grape variety and the vinegar
397 ageing. This group of compounds includes phenolic acids and phenolic aldehydes, as
398 well as oxidation and Maillard reaction products (present due to browning processes
399 and oxidative mechanisms taking place during ageing and storage), which have shown

400 maximum excitation/emission wavelengths around 330/420 nm (Airado-Rodríguez et
401 al., 2011; Azcarate et al., 2015; Callejón et al., 2012; Dufour et al., 2006;
402 Elcoroaristizabal et al., 2016; Sádecká & Tóthová, 2007). In contrast, in “*Condado de*
403 *Huelva*” PDO this F4 presents its excitation and emission maxima around 485/560 nm
404 ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}/\lambda_{\text{em}}$), and it could be associated with the aforementioned vitamin B2.

405 Finally, a fifth factor (F5, green line in Figure 2) appears only for the “*Vinagre de*
406 *Montilla-Moriles*” and “*Vinagre de Jerez*” PDOs, showing excitation and emission
407 maxima at 530/605 nm and 585/655 nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}/\lambda_{\text{em}}$), respectively. There are not reported
408 fluorophores matching exactly with this emission/excitation profile. However, it seems
409 to be related to the special characteristics of the category “*Pedro Ximenez*” for which a
410 higher mean values of this factor was detected in this category (Table V
411 Supplementary Material). The absence of this factor in the “*Vinagre Condado de*
412 *Huelva*” model also confirms this hypothesis since this sweet category is not registered
413 in this PDO.

414

415 **3.3 Vinegar category classification within each Spanish PDO**

416 Two different approaches, Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA)
417 and Support Vector Machines (SVM), were used for the development of classification
418 models of Spanish PDO vinegars according to their category. In all cases, the best
419 PLS-DA models were obtained using two latent variables (LVs). This optimum number
420 of LVs was chosen based on the Root Mean Square Error of Cross-Validation
421 (RMSECV), the ROC curves and de variance captured. On the other hand, the optimal
422 parameters for the optimization of SVM models, $\log_{10}(C)$ and $\log_{10}(\gamma)$, were found to
423 be 2 and between -2 and -0.5, respectively. The statistical assessment of the
424 performance of both classification models was carried out by calculating and
425 comparing different classifiers (described in section 2.3.2) such as sensitivity,
426 specificity and classification error of calibration (CAL), cross-validation (CV) and
427 prediction (PRED). These statistical results are shown in Table 2.

428 Regarding the PLS-DA models, high sensitivity and specificity values were
429 obtained for the sweet category (JPX and MPX) of “*Vinagre de Jerez*” and “*Vinagre de*
430 *Montilla-Moriles*” PDOs. The classification errors of prediction obtained for these
431 categories (100% of the samples correctly classified), demonstrated that these
432 samples can be successfully separated from the rest of classes. This is probably due to
433 their different chemical and fluorescence spectral features, since this sweet category
434 emitted at the longest wavelengths (Figure 1). In a similar way, concerning the non-

435 aged category (CSC) of “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDO, the different
436 fluorescence profile observed in the landscapes and the higher mean values of F1 and
437 F3 with respect to the rest of categories (Table V Supplementary Material), could be
438 related to the lowest errors of classification obtained for this category (25.0% of the
439 samples misclassified). However, unsatisfactory results were obtained for the rest of
440 aged categories within each Spanish PDO: JCR, JRE, MCR, CSO and CRE. The low
441 sensitivity and specificity values (mainly under 65.0%) and high classification errors
442 obtained in terms of prediction (between 25.0 and 63.0%), confirm the difficulty in
443 correctly classifying these aged vinegar categories (≥ 6 and ≥ 24 months) by using
444 linear classification models. This could be related to the similar score values followed
445 by the modelled factors of these categories within each Spanish PDOs (Table V
446 Supplementary Material). Among them, the ≥ 6 months aged samples (JCR, MCR and
447 CSO) were the worst classified ones in all the Spanish PDO vinegar models, showing
448 classification errors until 63.0%. This may be explained due to these wine vinegars are
449 aged over a wide range of time (from 6 to 24 months). Thus, those samples aged until
450 24 months are expected to be spectroscopically and chemically quite similar to the
451 vinegars of the following category (≥ 24 month). Similar results were obtained by
452 Callejón et al., (2012).

453 In contrast, higher sensitivity and specificity levels were obtained for all Spanish
454 PDO vinegars using SVM models (Table 2). The optimal parameters for the
455 optimization of SVM models, $\log_{10}(C)$ and $\log_{10}(\gamma)$, were optimized in the traditional
456 way by using an independent test set (Cristianini & Shawe-Taylor, 2000). Between
457 92% and 100% of the samples were correctly classified in all categories. Even more, all
458 samples belonging to the Spanish PDO “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” were perfectly
459 classified. Further information about the misclassified category samples within each
460 Spanish PDO is summarized in the confusion matrices shown in Table VI
461 (Supplementary Material). These results also point out that SVM does not need a large
462 number of samples to make a good model, as occurs in our study with some
463 categories, and further, it is not affected by the presence of outliers. These results
464 demonstrated that this methodology could be successfully used for the authentication
465 of the vinegar category belonging to each Spanish PDO.

466

467 **3.4 Spanish PDO classification within similar vinegar categories (“*Crianza*”,**
468 **“*Reserva*” and “*Pedro Ximenez*”)**

469 In this classification task, the objective was to classify the samples by their PDO for
470 a single category. Three PARAFAC models were built according to the vinegar
471 categories under study, i.e. “*Crianza*”, “*Reserva*” and “*Pedro Ximenez*”, in order to
472 discriminate their corresponding Spanish PDO. In a similar way to the previous
473 sections, the best PARAFAC models obtained for each vinegar category were selected
474 comparing the quality parameters of the models, which are shown in Table VII
475 (Supplementary Material). In this case, a 4-factor PARAFAC model was obtained for
476 “*Crianza*”, while a 5-factor PARAFAC model was built for “*Reserva*”, and a 3-factor
477 PARAFAC model was constructed for “*Pedro Ximenez*” category. The obtained models
478 explained more than 97.0% of the variance with a core consistency over zero. The
479 related PARAFAC loadings (excitation and emission spectra) obtained for the models
480 corresponding to each vinegar category are illustrated in Figure 3.

481 The maxima wavelengths (λ_{ex} and λ_{em}) of the different factors obtained for the
482 “*Crianza*”, “*Reserva*” and “*Pedro Ximenez*” PARAFAC models match with the different
483 fluorophores described in detail in section 3.2. As shown in **Figure 3**, the “*Crianza*”
484 category is characterized by factors with excitation and emission ranges between 340-
485 500 nm and 430-580 nm, respectively. These factors are mainly related to fluorescent
486 compounds naturally presented in high concentration in wine such as phenols,
487 flavonols and vitamins as previously described (section 3.2). These compounds have a
488 higher contribution in this category (Table V Supplementary Material) since the less
489 aged wine vinegars retain more compounds coming from the raw materials. Regarding
490 the “*Reserva*” samples, a higher number of factors were required to model this
491 category, i.e., more fluorescent compounds with a wide range of excitation/emission
492 spectra were needed to describe its underlying chemical composition. In this case, the
493 longer aging period undergone by vinegars of the “*Reserva*” category plays a crucial
494 role in this chemical complexity. There is an enrichment of these vinegars with more
495 phenolic compounds (released by the wood barrels) and oxidation products (derived
496 from the development of certain chemical reactions among vinegar components),
497 whose concentration levels have been proven to increase during the aging process
498 (Callejón, Morales, Silva Ferreira, & Troncoso, 2008). The wavelengths of the factors
499 modelled for “*Pedro Ximenez*” category are associated to fluorophores emitting at the
500 highest excitation and emission wavelengths (upper than 475 and 550 nm,
501 respectively). However, more information, not available in the literature, is needed to
502 identify these fluorophores.

503 For all the categories under study, the relative values of these factors (scores) vary
504 as a function of the Spanish PDO, which highlights that the composition of the vinegar

505 categories depends also on the raw material used (wine) and on the different
506 production methods to which the vinegars have been subjected in each PDO. Thus,
507 these particular characteristics reflected by the scores provide the chance to
508 discriminate the Spanish PDO corresponding to similar wine vinegar categories. In this
509 case, related to the proven higher ability of prediction previously obtained (Table 2),
510 only SVM classification models were built. The parameters for the optimization of the
511 SVM models, $\log_{10}(C)$ and $\log_{10}(\gamma)$, were found to be 2 and between -1 and 0,
512 respectively. Table 3 summarizes the statistical results (sensitivity, specificity and
513 errors) of the performance of the SVM models.

514 Regarding the “*Crianza*” category, high sensitivity and specificity values were
515 obtained for these samples according to their origin (Spanish PDO) with classification
516 errors of prediction lower than 3.5% (Table 3). These results demonstrate that it is
517 possible to successfully differentiate the Spanish PDO of “*Crianza*” vinegars according to
518 their fluorescent composition that is highly related to the raw material (wine) used.
519 Furthermore, all the samples belonging to the “*Pedro Ximenez*” category were correctly
520 classified in the “*Vinagre de Jerez*” and “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*” PDOs. The high
521 levels of sensitivity and specificity and the good classification rates obtained were
522 explained by the different production process employed by each Spanish PDO.
523 “*Reserva*” was the worst classified category according to the PDOs, showing sensitivity
524 and specificity values higher than 70% and predicted errors lower than 15%. In the
525 case of samples belonging to “*Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles*”, 100% of the “*Reserva*”
526 vinegars were correctly classified, and only some samples were misclassified between
527 “*Vinagre de Jerez*” and “*Vinagre de Condado de Huelva*” PDOs (Table VIII
528 Supplementary Material). These results are considered acceptable considering the
529 high variability of these samples due to the wide range of ageing periods that are
530 reflected by their complex chemical composition (Casale et al., 2006; García Parrilla et
531 al., 1999).

532

533 **4. Conclusions**

534 The analytical methodology proposed in this study, namely fluorescence
535 excitation–emission spectroscopy coupled to PARAFAC modeling and SVM
536 classification method, has demonstrated to be able to characterize and classify the
537 three Spanish PDOs wine vinegars according to their “Protected Denomination of
538 Origin” as well as their categories (aged and sweet). As a simple preliminary
539 characterization, a visual assessment of the fluorescence Excitation-Emission Matrices
540 (EEMs) of the aged categories pointed out similarities in the fluorescence landscapes

541 for the three Spanish PDOs wine vinegars: the spectral maxima were shifted towards
542 longer wavelengths with the aging of these vinegars. Moreover, the sweet category
543 “*Pedro Ximenez*” showed its excitation and emission maxima even at longer
544 wavelengths than the aged categories, probably due to the different production process
545 to which these vinegars are subjected. PARAFAC was carried out to spectroscopically
546 and chemically characterize the different wine vinegars. It gave information about the
547 potential fluorescent compounds present in the wine vinegars as well as their
548 contribution in each Spanish PDO and category. These dissimilar spectroscopic and
549 chemical features allowed us their differentiation according to their category and origin
550 (Spanish PDO) using suitable classification methods. The feasibility of SVM
551 methodology to classify the different categories of wine vinegars within each PDO was
552 successfully demonstrated. The built SVM classification models proved a higher ability
553 of prediction (between 92% and 100% correctly classified samples) than PLS-DA
554 models, especially for classifying aged vinegar categories with similar spectroscopic
555 characteristics. Furthermore, SVM models were also able to differentiate the Spanish
556 PDOs even for similar vinegar categories due to their spectral differences.

557 The advantages of this methodology, e.g. fast, non-destructive and non- sample
558 preparation, would allow implementing this method as an alternative tool for PDO
559 regulatory councils and producers to be implemented in routine analysis. It could be
560 applied for assessing the authenticity of the Spanish PDO and the vinegar category.
561 Finally, it is expected that further information about the specific ageing periods to which
562 these vinegars are subjected will improve the performance of some classification
563 models.

564

565 **5. Acknowledgments**

566 The authors want to thank “Consejería de Economía, Innovación y Ciencia” of the
567 “Junta de Andalucía” for the financial support provided through the project P12-AGR-
568 1601, and the Spanish Regulatory Councils of the wine vinegar PDOs for their
569 invaluable help with the acquisition of the samples for this study. In addition, authors
570 want to thanks “Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte” (MECD, Spanish
571 Government) for the FPU pre-doctoral fellowship and UPV/EHU (University of the
572 Basque Country) for the grant received from the program “*Contratación de Doctores*
573 *Recientes*”.

574

575 **6. References**

576 Aceña, L., Vera, L., Guasch, J., Busto, O., & Mestres, M. (2011). Chemical

577 characterization of commercial sherry vinegar aroma by headspace solid-phase
578 microextraction and gas chromatography-olfactometry. *Journal of Agricultural and*
579 *Food Chemistry*, 59(8), 4062–4070. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf104763u>

580 Acevedo, F. J., Jiménez, J., Maldonado, S., Domínguez, E., & Narváez, A. (2007).
581 Classification of wines produced in specific regions by UV-visible spectroscopy
582 combined with support vector machines. *Journal of Agricultural and Food*
583 *Chemistry*, 55(17), 6842–6849. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf070634q>

584 Airado-Rodríguez, D., Durán-Merás, I., Galeano-Díaz, T., & Wold, J. P. (2011). Front-
585 face fluorescence spectroscopy: A new tool for control in the wine industry.
586 *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 24(2), 257–264.
587 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2010.10.005>

588 Airado-Rodríguez, D., Galeano-Díaz, T., Durán-Merás, I., & Wold, J. P. (2009).
589 Usefulness of fluorescence excitation-emission matrices in combination with
590 parafac, as fingerprints of red wines. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*,
591 57(5), 1711–1720. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf8033623>

592 Andersen, C. M., & Bro, R. (2003). Practical aspects of PARAFAC modeling of
593 fluorescence excitation-emission data. *Journal of Chemometrics*, 17(4), 200–215.
594 <http://doi.org/10.1002/cem.790>

595 Azcarate, S. M., Araújo, A. De, Alcaraz, M. R., Ugulino, M. C., Araújo, D., Camiña, J.
596 M., & Goicoechea, H. C. (2015). Modeling excitation- emission fluorescence
597 matrices with pattern recognition algorithms for classification of Argentine white
598 wines according, 184, 214–219.

599 Azcarate, S. M., Cantarelli, M. A., Pellerano, R. G., Marchevsky, E. J., & Camiña, J. M.
600 (2013). Classification of argentinean sauvignon blanc wines by UV spectroscopy
601 and chemometric methods. *Journal of Food Science*, 78(3), 432–436.
602 <http://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.12060>

603 Bro, R. (1997). PARAFAC. Tutorial and applications. *Chemometrics and Intelligent*
604 *Laboratory Systems*, 38(2), 149–171. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7439(97)00032-4)
605 [7439\(97\)00032-4](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7439(97)00032-4)

606 Bro, R. (1998). Multi-way analysis in the food industry. Models, algorithms, and
607 applications., (1998).

608 Bro, R., & Kiers, H. A. L. (2003). A new efficient method for determining the number of
609 components in PARAFAC models. *Journal of Chemometrics*, 17(5), 274–286.

610 <http://doi.org/10.1002/cem.801>

611 Callejón, R. M., Amigo, J. M., Pairo, E., Garmón, S., Ocaña, J. A., & Morales, M. L.
612 (2012). Classification of Sherry vinegars by combining multidimensional
613 fluorescence, parafac and different classification approaches. *Talanta*, *88*, 456–
614 462. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2011.11.014>

615 Callejón, R. M., Morales, M. L., Silva Ferreira, A. C., & Troncoso, A. M. (2008).
616 Defining the typical aroma of Sherry vinegar: Sensory and chemical approach.
617 *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, *56*(17), 8086–8095.
618 <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf800903n>

619 Casale, M., Sáiz Abajo, M. J., González Sáiz, J. M., Pizarro, C., & Forina, M. (2006).
620 Study of the aging and oxidation processes of vinegar samples from different
621 origins during storage by near-infrared spectroscopy. *Analytica Chimica Acta*,
622 *557*(1–2), 360–366. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2005.10.063>

623 Christensen, J., Becker, E. M., & Frederiksen, C. S. (2005). Fluorescence
624 spectroscopy and PARAFAC in the analysis of yogurt. *Chemometrics and*
625 *Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, *75*(2), 201–208.
626 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2004.07.007>

627 Christiani, N., & Shawe-Taylor, J. (2000). An Introduction to Support Vector Machines.
628 *Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, UK.*

629 Cirlini, M., Caligiani, a., Palla, L., & Palla, G. (2011). HS-SPME/GC-MS and
630 chemometrics for the classification of Balsamic Vinegars of Modena of different
631 maturation and ageing. *Food Chemistry*, *124*(4), 1678–1683.
632 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.07.065>

633 Council Regulation (EC) No 510/2006 of 20 March 2006 on the protection of
634 geographical indications and designations of origin for agricultural products and
635 foodstuffs.

636 Cover, T., & Hart, P. (1967). Nearest neighbor pattern classification. *IEEE Transactions*
637 *on Information Theory*, *13*, 21 – 27.

638 Dufour, É., Letort, A., Laguet, A., Lebecque, A., & Serra, J. N. (2006). Investigation of
639 variety, typicality and vintage of French and German wines using front-face
640 fluorescence spectroscopy. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, *563*(1–2 SPEC. ISS.), 292–
641 299. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2005.11.005>

642 Elcoroaristizabal, S., Bro, R., García, J. A., & Alonso, L. (2015). PARAFAC models of

643 fluorescence data with scattering: A comparative study. *Chemometrics and*
644 *Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, 142, 124–130.
645 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2015.01.017>

646 Elcoroaristizabal, S., Callejón, R. M., Amigo, J. M., Ocaña-González, J. A., Morales, M.
647 L., & Ubeda, C. (2016). Fluorescence excitation-emission matrix spectroscopy as
648 a tool for determining quality of sparkling wines. *Food Chemistry*, 206, 284–290.
649 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.03.037>

650 García Parrilla, M. C., Heredia, F. J., & Troncoso, A. M. (1999). Sherry wine vinegars:
651 Phenolic composition changes during aging. *Food Research International*, 32(6),
652 433–440. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969\(99\)00105-2](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969(99)00105-2)

653 Joint FAO/WHO Food Standards Programme. Report No: FAO-ESN-CX/PFV-98/8.
654 Codex Committee on Processed Fruits and Vegetables. Sess 19. Whashington,
655 DC, 16-18, March 1998. FAO, R. Conversion of European Regional Standard for
656 Vinegar into World-wide Standard. (1998).

657 Karoui, R., & Blecker, C. (2011). Fluorescence Spectroscopy Measurement for Quality
658 Assessment of Food Systems-a Review. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, 4(3),
659 364–386. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s11947-010-0370-0>

660 Karoui, R., Dufour, É., & De Baerdemaeker, J. (2006). Front face fluorescence
661 spectroscopy coupled with chemometric tools for monitoring the oxidation of semi-
662 hard cheeses throughout ripening. *Food Chemistry*, 101(3), 1305–1314.
663 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2006.01.028>

664 Lenhardt, L., Bro, R., Zeković, I., Dramićanin, T., & Dramićanin, M. D. (2015).
665 Fluorescence spectroscopy coupled with PARAFAC and PLS DA for
666 characterization and classification of honey. *Food Chemistry*, 175, 284–291.
667 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.11.162>

668 Liu, F., He, Y., & Wang, L. (2008). Determination of effective wavelengths for
669 discrimination of fruit vinegars using near infrared spectroscopy and multivariate
670 analysis. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 615(1), 10–17.
671 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2008.03.030>

672 Margraf, T., Santos, É. N. T., de Andrade, E. F., van Ruth, S. M., & Granato, D. (2016).
673 Effects of geographical origin, variety and farming system on the chemical
674 markers and in vitro antioxidant capacity of Brazilian purple grape juices. *Food*
675 *Research International*, 82, 145–155. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2016.02.003>

- 676 Morales, M. L., Tesfaye, W., García-Parrilla, M. C., Casas, J. a, & Troncoso, A. M.
677 (2002). Evolution of the aroma profile of sherry wine vinegars during an
678 experimental aging in wood. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 50(11),
679 3173–8. <http://doi.org/10.1021/jf011313w>
- 680 Nocairi, H., Qannari, E. M., Vigneau, E., & Bertrand, D. (2005). Discrimination on latent
681 components with respect to patterns. Application to multicollinear data.
682 *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis*, 48(1), 139–147.
683 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2003.09.008>
- 684 Polo M.C., & Sanchez-Luengo, A. (1991). El vinagre de vino. In *in: C. Llaguno, M.C.*
685 *Polo (Eds.), El vinagre de vino, C.S.I.C. Espana, Madrid* (pp. 23–47).
- 686 Rodríguez-Delgado, M. A., Malovaná, S., Pérez, J. P., Borges, T., & García
687 Montelongo, F. J. (2001). Separation of phenolic compounds by high-performance
688 liquid chromatography with absorbance and fluorimetric detection. *Journal of*
689 *Chromatography A*, 912(2), 249–257. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(01)00598-2)
690 [9673\(01\)00598-2](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(01)00598-2)
- 691 Sádecká, J., & Tóthová, J. (2007). Fluorescence Spectroscopy and Chemometrics in
692 the Food Classification− a Review. *Czech J. Food Sci. Vol*, 25(4), 159–
693 173. Retrieved from <http://www.journals.uzpi.cz/publicFiles/00302.pdf>
- 694 Sádecká, J., Tóthová, J., & Májek, P. (2009). Classification of brandies and wine
695 distillates using front face fluorescence spectroscopy. *Food Chemistry*, 117(3),
696 491–498. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2009.04.053>
- 697 Tena, N., Aparicio, R., & García-González, D. L. (2012). Chemical changes of
698 thermoxidized virgin olive oil determined by excitation-emission fluorescence
699 spectroscopy (EEFS). *Food Research International*, 45(1), 103–108.
700 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2011.10.015>
- 701 Tóthová, J., & Sádecká, L. Ž. J. (2008). Characterization and Classification of Distilled
702 Drinks Using Total Luminescence and Synchronous Fluorescence Spectroscopy.
703 *Acta Chimica Slovaca*, 1(1), 265–275.
- 704 Vapnik, V. (1999). The Nature of Statistical Learning Theory . In *New York : Springer-*
705 *Verlag.*
- 706 Wold, H. (1966). Estimation of principal components and related models by iterative
707 least squares . In *In: Multivariate Analysis (Krishnaiah PR , ed.)*. *New York :*
708 *Academic Press .*

- 709 Wold, S. (1976). Pattern recognition by means of disjoint principal components models
710 . *Pattern Recognition*, 8, 127 – 139.
- 711 Xu, Y., Zomer, S., & Brereton, R. G. (2006). Support Vector Machines: A Recent
712 Method for Classification in Chemometrics. *Critical Reviews in Analytical*
713 *Chemistry*, 36(3–4), 177–188. <http://doi.org/10.1080/10408340600969486>
- 714 Zhu, D., Ji, B., Eum, H. L., & Zude, M. (2009). Evaluation of the non-enzymatic
715 browning in thermally processed apple juice by front-face fluorescence
716 spectroscopy. *Food Chemistry*, 113(1), 272–279.
717 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2008.07.009>

718

719 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

720 **Figure 1.** *Excitation-Emission fluorescence landscapes obtained for different*
721 *categories of Spanish PDO vinegars. The color scale of fluorescence intensity (in*
722 *arbitrary units) varies from dark blue (lowest signal intensity) to yellow (highest signal*
723 *intensity). The acronyms for the different wine vinegar categories are defined in Table 1.*

724

725 **Figure 2.** *Excitation and Emission spectra (PARAFAC loadings) of the main*
726 *fluorophores present in the vinegars of the three Spanish PDOs.*

727

728 **Figure 3.** *Excitation and Emission spectra (PARAFAC loadings) of the main*
729 *fluorophores present in different vinegars categories of the Spanish PDOs.*

730

731 **Table 1.** Wine vinegar samples analyzed according to the Spanish PDOs

<i>Protected Designation of Origin (PDO)</i>	<i>Vinegar Category</i>	<i>Category Name</i>	<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Aging time (months)</i>	<i>Number of samples*</i>
<i>“Vinagre de Jerez”</i>	Aged	“Vinagre de Jerez”	JCR	≥6	13
		“Reserva”	JRE	≥24	11
		“Gran Reserva”	JGR	≥ 120	2
	Sweet	“Pedro Ximenez”	JPX	-	4
<i>“Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles”</i>	Aged	“Crianza”	MCR	≥6	7
		“Reserva”	MRE	≥24	4
		“Gran Reserva”	MGR	≥120	2
	Sweet	“Pedro Ximenez”	MPX	-	5
<i>“Vinagre de Condado de Huelva”</i>	Non – aged	“Vinagre Condado de Huelva”	CSC	0	6
	Aged	“Viejo Solera”	CSO	≥6	6
		“Viejo Reserva”	CRE	≥24	7
		“Viejo Añada”	CAN	≥36	2

732

733 *Note: each sample- corresponds to different producers

734

735 **Table 2.** Sensitivity, specificity and classification errors (%) obtained for SVM and PLS-
 736 DA classification models corresponding to the vinegar category of each Spanish PDO.

737

Spanish PDO	"Vinagre de Jerez"						"Vinagre de Montilla-Moriles"						"Vinagre de Condado de Huelva"					
	SVM			PLS-DA			SVM			PLS-DA			SVM			PLS-DA		
Category	J C R	J R E	J P X	J C R	J R E	J P X	M C R	M R E	M P X	M C R	M R E	M P X	C S C	C S O	C R E	C S C	C S O	C R E
Sensitivity CAL	92 .9	92 .3	10 0	3 8. 7	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	80 .0	10 0.	10 0.	83 .3	10 0.	10 0.	75 .0	10 0.	10 0.
Sensitivity CV	10 0	10 0	10 0	3 8. 7	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	80 .0	66 .7	10 0	10 0	10 0	10 0	75 .0	10 0	10 0
Sensitivity PRED	92 .9	92 .3	10 0	1 0.	66 .7	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	50 .0	10 0.	10 0.	83 .3	10 0.	10 0.	50 .0	10 0.	10 0.
Specificity CAL	10 0.	94 .4	96 .3	9 0.	32 .5	94 .5	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	83 .3	75 .0	10 0.	10 0.	92 .3	10 0.	10 0.	33 .3	62 .5
Specificity CV	10 0	10 0	10 0	9 0.	25 .0	94 .5	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	83 .3	62 .5	95 .8	10 0	10 0	10 0	10 0.	25 .9	62 .5
Specificity PRED	10 0	94 .4	96 .3	7 5.	18 .2	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	10 0.	91 .7	10 0.	10 0.	0 0.	25 .0
Class. Error CAL	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	3 5. 1	33 .7	2. 7	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	18 .3	12 .5	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	12 .5	33 .3	18 .7
Class. Error CV	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	3 5. 1	37 .5	2. 7	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	18 .3	35 .4	2. 1	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	12 .5	37 .0	18 .7
Class. Error PRED	3. 5	6. 6	1. 8	6 2. 5	57 .5	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	0. 0	25 .0	0. 0	0. 0	8. 3	4. 1	0. 0	25 .0	50 .0	37 .5

738

739

740 **Table 3.** Sensitivity, specificity and classification errors (%) obtained for Spanish PDO
 741 classification models in similar wine vinegar categories.

742

743

744

745

746

747

748

749

750

751

752

753

754

755

756

757

758

759

760

761

762

763

Category	CR			RE			PX	
Classification model	SVM			SVM			SVM	
Spanish PDO	JCR	MCR	CSO	JRE	MRE	CRE	JPX	MPX
Sensitivity CAL	92.9	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	71.4	100.0	100.0
Sensitivity CV	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Sensitivity PRED	92.9	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	71.4	100.0	100.0
Specificity CAL	100.0	95.0	100.0	81.8	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Specificity CV	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Specificity PRED	100.0	95.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	0.71.4	100.0	100.0
Class. Error CAL	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Class. Error CV	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Class. Error PRED	3.5	2.5	0.0	9.1	0.0	14.3	0.0	0.0

764

765

766

767

768

769

770

771

772